

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Liao, Y., & Meng, Li. (2024). Analysis of the Relationship between China's "One Country, Two Systems" and the Chinese National Community. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(4), 152-165.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.04.534

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Analysis of the Relationship between China's "One Country, Two Systems" and the Chinese National Community

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Abstract

As a great initiative of socialism with Chinese characteristics, "One Country, Two Systems" not only successfully solved the governance problems after the return of Hong Kong and Macao but also profoundly influenced the national process of the Chinese nation. This paper explores the profound impact of "One Country, Two Systems" on the Chinese nation in terms of institutional arrangements, political integration, economic integration, and social and cultural exchanges. It analyzes its promoting role in the political identity, economic process, and social and cultural identity of the Chinese nation and advocates the establishment of the "Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Fujian Taiwan Zhang Honghua National Community Construction Pilot Zone" to promote the construction of the "One China" for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. Through in-depth analysis of the practical effectiveness of "One Country, Two Systems," this article aims to stimulate further thinking and discussion among experts and scholars on the relationship between "One Country, Two Systems" and the Chinese national community.

Keywords: "One Country, Two Systems," Chinese Nation, Ethnic Process, Political Identification, Economic Integration, Social and Cultural Identity, Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Fujian Taiwan Zhang Honghua Ethnic Community Construction Pilot Zone

1. Introduction

In the late 1990s, the sovereignty of Hong Kong and Macao successively returned to China, demonstrating the success of the "one country, two systems" (i.e., "one country, two systems") solution to international historical legacy issues.

Since the return of Hong Kong and Macao to China more than 20 years ago, their overall political, economic, and social development has been good, indicating that the "One Country, Two Systems" plan is not only feasible but also in line with China's national conditions and the public opinion of Hong Kong and Macao society. For a long time, scholars from China and countries such as the UK and the US have paid considerable attention to the study of Hong Kong and Macao. However, research on linking "One Country, Two Systems" with the community of the

Chinese nation is rare. China is a civilization with a long history, and the Chinese nation is a wise Eastern nation. Through the study of "One Country, Two Systems" in Hong Kong and Macao, we can better understand the Chinese wisdom, solutions, and the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. Why is this problem important?

2. A brief literature review

In recent years, there has been a high level of research and fruitful results in the domestic academic community on patriotism, the Chinese nation, the Chinese national community, and the awareness of the Chinese national community. However, from the perspective of ethnic processes, the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) database searches for words such as "Hong Kong and Macao ethnic groups" and "ethnic processes" simultaneously, and there are currently no relevant research results on the ethnic processes of Hong Kong and Macao.

The research of Chinese Mainland scholars on the theory of national process is mainly seen in some articles of the former Soviet Union scholars' national process theory translated and introduced in the National Translation Series (now World Nationalities) in the 1980s. In the 1990s, WANG Xi-en (1998) from the Institute of Ethnic Studies of the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences published his doctoral thesis "Ethnic Processes and States," which is regarded as an important representative work in the theoretical research of ethnic processes in China.

LIAO Yang (1998, 1999, 2000, 2001, 2003, 2005, 2021) analyzed issues related to ethnic groups and identity in Hong Kong and Macao, while PAN Guohua (2004) analyzed the relationship between the Hong Kong model and the future of Taiwan. ZHOU Da-ming (1996, 1997, 2000), SUN Jiu-xia (2000), and SHAO Zong-hai (2011) discussed the social structure and ethnic relations in Macao. HAO Shinan (2019) discussed the national identity of Hong Kong people.

In recent years, experts and scholars such as HAO Shiyuan (2021, 2022), SONG Caifa (2021), GAO Yongjiu (2019, 2021, 202, 320, 2024), HH Ming et al. (2020, 2023), Naribiligo et al. (2020, 2021, 2023), QING Jue et al. (2018, 2024), WU Xiao-hua (2018, 2023), LIU Yonggang (2021), LIU Baoming et al. (2021) have conducted relevant research on the sense of community of the Chinese nation.

It is worth noting that in recent years, journals such as Guangxi Ethnic Studies, Ethnic Studies Journal, Journal of Central University for Nationalities, and Journal of Central South University for Nationalities have increased their publication efforts on topics related to the Chinese national community, publishing special issues or columns on strengthening the awareness of the Chinese national community.

Scholars from other countries have rarely conducted direct research on the relationship between the "One Country, Two Systems" policy in Hong Kong and Macao and the community of the Chinese nation, but there are also a few scholars who have conducted research in certain areas. For example, Amy L. Freedman (2000) conducted empirical research to examine the political participation and ethnic identity issues of Chinese overseas communities in Indonesia, Malaysia, and the United States.

Ane Bislev (2014) bridges the cognitive gap between China and the West by analyzing the conceptualization of "Chinese nationalism" and discussing the differences between patriotism and nationalism, as well as their exchange in contemporary China. D. Grossworth Kachtan (2017) examines the process of "acting ethnicity" and demonstrates that, in certain circumstances, people act in keeping with an ethnic identity. Naoko Takei (2021) explores the construction process of ethnic meaning using Japanese mixed-race children as an example.

Nurhayat Bilge (2019) uses principles of Cultural Fusion Theory (Croucher & Kramer, 2017), this study focuses on representations of Syrian refugees in mainstream Turkish newspapers to determine. Ming tak Chew and Matthew (2021) analyzed how the commercialization of subordinate races and ethnicities (CPOARAE) generates boundary processes that disrupt established ethnic and racial hierarchies. Isabella Ng(2023)explores an unusual multi-ethnic cluster in a walled village in rural Hong Kong.

The review of academic history shows that there is almost no research on the integration of the "One Country, Two Systems" policy in Hong Kong and Macao with the national process of the Chinese national community, and there is a lack of research on the construction of the Chinese national community in the Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Greater Bay Area from the perspective of national process theory.

3. The institutional arrangement of "One Country, Two Systems" and the institutional innovation of the return of sovereignty of Hong Kong and Macao to the big family of the Chinese nation

The proposal of "one country, two systems" is a major strategic decision made by the CPC to solve the historical problems of Hong Kong and Macao. This institutional innovation not only maintains national sovereignty and territorial integrity, but also respects the history and current situation of Hong Kong and Macao, achieving a win-win situation for national unity and regional prosperity.

3.1 The milestone of Hong Kong and Macao sovereignty returning to China

The return of sovereignty over Hong Kong and Macao to China is an important milestone in the history of the Chinese nation. Through the institutional arrangement of "One Country, Two Systems," Hong Kong and Macao have smoothly returned to the embrace of the motherland and become special administrative regions of the People's Republic of China, while maintaining the original capitalist system and way of life unchanged. This historic transformation not only demonstrates China's national strength and international status, but also deeply reflects the Chinese nation's firm pursuit of unity and solidarity.

3.2 Practice of institutional innovation

The core of 'One Country, Two Systems' lies in the organic combination of the foundation of 'One Country' and the benefits of 'Two Systems.' Under the premise of 'one country,' Hong Kong and Macao enjoy a high degree of autonomy, including administrative power, legislative power, independent judicial power, and final adjudication power. At the same time, the central government is responsible for diplomatic and defense affairs in Hong Kong and Macao, ensuring national unity and security. This institutional innovation not only ensures the long-term stability and development of Hong Kong and Macao, but also provides useful reference for the international community to solve similar problems.

4. The Relationship between Ethnic Processes and National Politics

Ethnic processes, as an important field of sociological and anthropological research, involve multiple levels such as ethnic formation, evolution, interaction, and integration. This process not only concerns the survival and development of the nation itself, but also has a profound impact on the stability and prosperity of multi-ethnic countries.

4.1 How to understand ethnic processes?

The ethnic process is a dynamic, complex, and continuous process that encompasses multiple stages of ethnic formation, development, transformation, and integration. In this process, factors such as ethnic culture, ethnic identity, and ethnic relations are intertwined, jointly shaping the characteristics and destiny of the nation. The ethnic process is not only a historical process, but also a social process that constantly evolves with the development of the times and changes in society.

What is the relationship between ethnic processes and multi-ethnic countries? A multi-ethnic country refers to a country composed of multiple ethnic groups, with rich and diverse ethnic cultures and ethnic relationships within it.

The ethnic process is of great significance for the stability and development of multi-ethnic countries. On the one hand, the smooth progress of ethnic processes helps to enhance unity and harmony among various ethnic groups,

promote political stability and economic development within the country; On the other hand, contradictions and conflicts in ethnic processes may also pose a threat to national stability, and even trigger social unrest and division. Therefore, multi-ethnic countries need to handle ethnic relations properly and promote the healthy development of ethnic processes.

4.2 The impact of political integration within ethnic states on ethnic processes

The successful practice of "One Country, Two Systems" has not only achieved political stability in Hong Kong and Macao, but also promoted the political identity and cohesion of the Chinese nation.

(1) The cornerstone of political stability

The 'One Country, Two Systems' policy has provided a stable political environment for the Hong Kong and Macao regions. Under the premise of 'one country,' Hong Kong and Macao enjoy a high degree of autonomy, avoiding political turmoil caused by institutional differences. At the same time, the central government guarantees the legitimate rights and interests of Hong Kong and Macao through the Constitution and Basic Law, ensuring the long-term stability of the region. These examples illustrate that political stability and social stability are prerequisites and foundations for economic and social development.

The practice of "One Country, Two Systems" has deepened the sense of identity and belonging of residents in Hong Kong and Macao towards the Chinese nation. On the basis of common cultural traditions and national feelings, residents of Hong Kong and Macao have gradually realized that they are not only Hong Kong and Macao people, but also Chinese people. The deepening of this political identity provides a solid political foundation for the unity and solidarity of the Chinese nation.

(2) Political integration and deepening of national identity

Political integration refers to the state adjusting and coordinating the relationships between various ethnic groups through political means and policy measures to achieve national unity and stability.

The impact of political integration on ethnic processes is mainly reflected in the following aspects: firstly, by formulating and implementing ethnic policies, promoting equality, unity, and common development among all ethnic groups; Secondly, by strengthening education on ethnic unity, we can enhance the sense of identity and belonging of all ethnic groups to the country; The third is to promote the economic and social development of ethnic regions, improve their living standards and comprehensive competitiveness. These measures help promote the positive development of ethnic processes and promote the harmony and stability of multi-ethnic countries.

(3) How to view the national process of the Chinese nation in the era of globalization?

The era of globalization has brought new opportunities and challenges to the national process of the Chinese nation. On the one hand, globalization has promoted communication and integration among different ethnic groups, providing a broader space for the cultural inheritance and innovation of the Chinese nation; On the other hand, globalization has also intensified competition and conflicts among ethnic groups, posing new challenges to the national identity and security of the Chinese nation. Therefore, in the context of globalization, the Chinese nation needs to actively promote the healthy development of the national process, strengthening national unity and cohesion while maintaining cultural diversity and innovation. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen international exchanges and cooperation to enhance the influence and competitiveness of the Chinese nation on the global stage.

In short, the ethnic process is a complex and important social phenomenon that is related to the stability and prosperity of multi-ethnic countries, as well as the survival and development of various ethnic groups.

5. From the perspective of national process theory, 'One Country, Two Systems'

5.1 From the perspective of ethnic process theory, 'One Country, Two Systems'

The ethnic process is a complex historical process involving the formation, development, evolution, and extinction of ethnic groups. Under this theoretical framework, "One Country, Two Systems" as a great initiative of socialism with Chinese characteristics essentially involves implementing two different social systems within the territory of a country. This institutional arrangement is not only an innovation of traditional ethnic political theory, but also an enrichment and development of ethnic process theory.

5.2 *The Interwoven Relationship between Ethnic Political Processes and "One Country, Two Systems"*

(1) The connotation of ethnic political process

The process of ethnic politics refers to the process in which ethnic groups seek to express their rights, participate in national governance, and build ethnic identity in the political field. This process involves the struggle for ethnic autonomy, the formulation and implementation of ethnic policies, and the adjustment and harmony of ethnic relations.

(2) The mechanism of political integration

The political integration of nation states aims to ensure equal participation and common development of all ethnic groups in politics through institutional design and policy implementation. This includes establishing a multi-ethnic inclusive political system, implementing regional ethnic autonomy, and promoting political mutual trust and cooperation among all ethnic groups.

(3) The Construction of Political Identity

Political identity is the cornerstone of the stability and development of a nation-state. Through the positive guidance of ethnic policies, the common promotion of ethnic culture, and the education and popularization of ethnic history, it is possible to effectively enhance the sense of belonging and identity of various ethnic groups towards the country. For example, China's concept of "Chinese national community" aims to strengthen the common historical memory and cultural identity of all ethnic groups, promote political integration, and deepen national identity.

Overall, the process of ethnic politics involves the formation of ethnic political entities, the adjustment of ethnic political relations, and the development and evolution of ethnic politics. In the practice of 'One Country, Two Systems,' the differences in political systems have not hindered the unity of the country and the solidarity of the nation. On the contrary, through the design of the special administrative region system, Hong Kong and Macao have achieved positive interaction and common development with the mainland while maintaining their original political system and social stability. This political flexibility and inclusiveness provide the possibility for harmonious coexistence among different ethnic political entities.

5.3 *The mutual promotion between the national economic process and "One Country, Two Systems"*

The process of ethnic economy is the material foundation of ethnic development, involving the formation, development, and interaction with other ethnic economies. The 'One Country, Two Systems' policy not only promotes the economic development of Hong Kong and Macao, but also enhances the overall economic process of the Chinese nation.

(1) Characteristics of Ethnic Economic Processes

The process of ethnic economy refers to the interaction and cooperation among various ethnic groups in economic activities, including resource allocation, industrial development, market circulation, and other aspects. This process is often influenced by multiple factors such as geographical environment, historical traditions, and policy orientation.

Under the framework of "One Country, Two Systems," the economic cooperation between the mainland and Hong Kong and Macao has become increasingly close, forming an economic development pattern of complementary advantages and mutual benefit. By utilizing their respective economic advantages and resource endowments, we have achieved common prosperity and development in the economy. This economic integration and interaction have injected new impetus into the continuous advancement of the national economic process.

(2) The Path of Economic Integration

The economic integration of nation states aims to achieve common prosperity among all ethnic groups by optimizing resource allocation, promoting regional coordinated development, and strengthening economic capacity building in ethnic regions. This requires the national level to formulate differentiated economic policies, support the development of characteristic industries in ethnic regions, and strengthen infrastructure construction to narrow the regional development gap.

The 'One Country, Two Systems' policy provides vast economic development space for Hong Kong and Macao regions. With strong support from the central government, Hong Kong and Macao have fully leveraged their unique geographical and institutional advantages to become an important bridge connecting the mainland and international markets. At the same time, the booming development of finance, trade, tourism and other industries in Hong Kong and Macao has injected new vitality into the economic development of the Chinese nation.

(3) The dependence and development of the economy of Hong Kong and Macao Special Administrative Regions and the economy of the Chinese nation

The 'One Country, Two Systems' policy has promoted the coordinated development of the Chinese nation's economic process. Under the premise of 'one country,' economic cooperation between Hong Kong, Macao and the mainland is becoming increasingly close. By signing agreements such as the Mainland and Hong Kong Closer Economic Partnership Arrangement (CEPA) and the Mainland and Macao Closer Economic Partnership Arrangement, the Hong Kong and Macao regions have achieved a mutually beneficial and complementary economic development pattern with the mainland.

Through the construction of the Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Greater Bay Area, the Hong Kong and Macao regions can better integrate into China's national development, and the advantages of "one country" and "two systems" can be fully utilized in regional economic development and the economic development of the Chinese nation.

5.4 *The Harmonious Coexistence of Ethnic Social Processes and 'One Country, Two Systems'*

(1) The Basic Dimensions of Ethnic Social Processes

The process of ethnic society involves dynamic changes in the social structure, social interactions, and social relationships of ethnic groups. This process is related to social fairness and justice, ethnic unity, and social stability.

The process of ethnic society is the social aspect of ethnic life, including the structure, function, and changes of ethnic society. The "One Country, Two Systems" policy has not only promoted economic exchanges between Hong Kong, Macao and the mainland, but also facilitated social exchanges and integration between Hong Kong, Macao and Guangdong, enhancing the social and cultural identity of the Chinese nation.

(2) Integration strategy of ethnic society

The key to social integration in nation states lies in building an inclusive social environment that promotes mutual understanding and respect among different ethnic groups. This includes promoting multicultural education, strengthening community building for ethnic integration, and improving mechanisms for mediating ethnic conflicts.

(3) Strengthening ethnic and social identity

The key to social integration in nation states lies in building an inclusive social environment that promotes mutual understanding and respect among different ethnic groups. This includes promoting multicultural education, strengthening community building for ethnic integration, and improving mechanisms for mediating ethnic conflicts.

In the practice of "One Country, Two Systems," social stability and improvement of people's livelihoods in Hong Kong and Macao have been effectively guaranteed. By strengthening social management and public services, the government of the special administrative region has successfully maintained social harmony and stability, and improved the living standards of the people. This kind of harmonious coexistence at the social level provides strong guarantees for the smooth progress of the national social process.

5.5 *The mutual nourishment between ethnic cultural processes and 'One Country, Two Systems'*

(1) Characteristics of Ethnic Cultural Processes

The process of ethnic culture refers to the dynamic development of ethnic groups in cultural inheritance, innovation, and exchange. This process is crucial for building national identity, maintaining cultural diversity, and enhancing cultural confidence.

Through cultural exchanges and cooperation with the mainland, the cultural industry of the special administrative region has also made significant progress. This cultural mutual nourishment and integration not only enriches the cultural treasure trove of the Chinese nation, but also promotes the diversity and inclusiveness of national culture.

(2) Ways of cultural integration

The process of ethnic culture is the process of inheriting, integrating, innovating, and developing ethnic culture. Under the "One Country, Two Systems" policy, the cultural characteristics of Hong Kong and Macao have been fully protected and inherited.

The cultural integration of nation states aims to promote the mainstream culture of the country while protecting and inheriting the excellent traditional culture of various ethnic groups, achieving the organic combination of cultural diversity and unity. This requires the formulation of cultural protection policies at the national level, strengthening the protection of cultural heritage, and promoting innovative development of the cultural industry.

(3) Deepening cultural identity

Cultural identity is the core of the cohesion of a nation-state. By strengthening ethnic cultural education, promoting ethnic cultural exchanges, and creating cultural brands with national characteristics, we can deepen the cultural identity of various ethnic groups towards the country. For example, China's "the Belt and Road" initiative has not only promoted economic cooperation among countries along the Belt and Road, but also strengthened cultural exchanges and mutual learning, providing cultural support for building a community with a shared future for mankind.

The practice of 'One Country, Two Systems' has enhanced the social and cultural identity of the Chinese nation. On the basis of common cultural traditions and ethnic emotions, the cultural identity and sense of belonging between residents of Hong Kong, Macao and mainland China have gradually strengthened. The enhancement of

this social and cultural identity provides a solid cultural foundation for the unity and solidarity of the Chinese nation.

In summary, "One Country, Two Systems" as an important institutional arrangement of socialism with Chinese characteristics not only conforms to the objective laws of the national process, but also provides strong support for the comprehensive development of national politics, economy, society, and culture.

6. Chinese national identity and forging a sense of community for the Chinese nation

6.1 Multidimensional Understanding of Ethnic Identity

Ethnic identity, as a complex and multi-level concept, encompasses multiple aspects of an individual's cognition, emotional belonging, and behavioral tendencies towards their ethnic group. At the theoretical level, ethnic identity is a common focus of attention in multiple disciplines such as ethnology, sociology, psychology, etc. It involves multiple relationships such as individual and collective, culture and identity, history and reality. From a practical perspective, ethnic identity is an important manifestation of the cohesion and centripetal force of a country and a nation, and is a key factor in maintaining ethnic unity and social stability.

To understand ethnic identity, it is first necessary to clarify that it is a dynamic process of development. With the changes of the times, the evolution of society, and the exchange and integration of cultures, the connotation and extension of national identity are constantly enriched and expanded. Therefore, we cannot simply view ethnic identity as a fixed and unchanging state, but rather as a constantly evolving and changing process.

6.2 The Rich Connotation and Profound Significance of Chinese National Identity

As a special ethnic identity, Chinese national identity has its unique connotation and significance. It includes multiple aspects such as identity recognition as a member of the Chinese nation, recognition of the history, culture, and traditions of the Chinese nation, and recognition of the common interests and destiny of the Chinese nation. This identification is not only reflected in the individual's psychological level, but also in the cultural and political levels of society.

How to view Chinese national identity? We should adopt a comprehensive and in-depth perspective.

Firstly, Chinese national identity is the foundation of the unity and solidarity of the Chinese nation. In the diverse and integrated family of the Chinese nation, the identification between different ethnic groups is an important bond to maintain ethnic unity and promote social harmony.

Secondly, Chinese national identity is a manifestation of cultural confidence in the Chinese nation. By recognizing and inheriting our own national culture, we can enhance cultural confidence and promote Chinese culture to the world.

Finally, Chinese national identity is the spiritual driving force for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. In the historical process of realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, it is necessary to gather the wisdom and strength of the entire nation, and Chinese national identity is the source of this strength.

6.3 The close connection between Chinese national identity and forging a sense of community for the Chinese nation

There is a close connection between Chinese national identity and forging a sense of community for the Chinese nation.

On the one hand, Chinese national identity is the foundation and prerequisite for forging a sense of community among the Chinese nation. Only when we have a profound understanding and recognition of our national identity,

historical culture, and common interests can we truly form a sense of belonging and responsibility towards the Chinese national community.

On the other hand, forging a sense of community among the Chinese nation can further deepen and consolidate the identity of the Chinese nation. By strengthening education on ethnic unity and promoting exchanges and integration among different ethnic groups, we can continuously enhance the cohesion and centripetal force of the Chinese nation, thereby further consolidating and developing the Chinese national identity.

6.4 Strategies for Enhancing Chinese National Identity and Strengthening Community Awareness in the Era of Globalization

In the era of globalization, facing the impact and challenges of multiculturalism, how to enhance Chinese national identity and strengthen the sense of community of the Chinese nation has become an urgent problem to be solved. We can start with the following aspects:

Firstly, strengthen the inheritance and promotion of the historical and cultural heritage of the Chinese nation. By delving deeper into and organizing the historical and cultural resources of the Chinese nation, strengthening its promotion and publicity, we can enable more people to understand and recognize the history and culture of the Chinese nation, thereby enhancing their sense of national identity and belonging.

Secondly, promote communication, exchange, and integration among various ethnic groups. By organizing various forms of ethnic cultural activities, exchange activities, etc., we promote mutual understanding and respect among different ethnic groups, enhance friendship and cooperation, and thus promote the unity and progress of the Chinese nation.

Once again, strengthen guidance and support at the national level. The government can encourage and support ethnic cultural inheritance and innovation in various ethnic regions by formulating relevant policies and providing financial support, promoting the prosperity and development of Chinese national culture.

Finally, pay attention to cultivating the national consciousness and patriotism of young people. By strengthening guidance and education in school and family education, we aim to cultivate a sense of national pride and patriotism among young people, enabling them to become the backbone of inheriting and promoting Chinese culture.

6.5 The Path to Strengthening National Identity and Community Consciousness in the Process of the Great Rejuvenation of the Chinese Nation

In the historical process of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, strengthening national identity and forging a sense of community for the Chinese nation has important strategic significance. To achieve this goal, we need to make efforts in the following aspects:

One is to adhere to the development concept of putting the people at the center. In the process of promoting economic and social development, it is necessary to fully consider the interests and needs of all ethnic groups, ensure that they share the fruits of reform and development, and enhance their sense of identity and belonging to the Chinese nation.

The second is to strengthen the construction of ethnic unity and progress. By carrying out activities to promote ethnic unity and progress, strengthening propaganda and education on ethnic unity, and other means, we aim to create a favorable atmosphere for all ethnic groups to unite and strive for common prosperity and development, providing strong spiritual support for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

The third is to promote the innovative development and creative transformation of excellent traditional Chinese culture. While inheriting and promoting the excellent traditional Chinese culture, we should pay attention to its

integration with modern civilization, promote its innovative development and creative transformation, and make it shine more brilliantly in the new era.

The fourth is to strengthen international exchanges and cooperation. By strengthening exchanges and cooperation with other countries and regions, showcasing the unique charm and value of Chinese culture, enhancing the influence and discourse power of the Chinese nation on the international stage, and creating a favorable international environment for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

In summary, ethnic identity is a complex and profound topic that involves multiple relationships such as individual and collective, culture and identity, history and reality. In the era of globalization and the historical process of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, it is necessary to enhance the identity of the Chinese nation and forge a sense of community for the Chinese nation through various ways and means, providing a solid ideological foundation and spiritual motivation for realizing the Chinese Dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

7. From Strengthening the Awareness of the Chinese National Community to Building the Chinese National Community

In the splendid history of the Chinese nation for over 5000 years (some say nearly 10000 years), all ethnic groups have jointly written brilliant cultural chapters and forged an indestructible national spirit. In today's era, with the deepening of globalization and profound changes in Chinese society, how to understand and strengthen the sense of community of the Chinese nation, explore the relationship between the sense of community of the Chinese nation, the shared spiritual home of the Chinese nation, and the identity of the Chinese nation, and build a community of the Chinese nation has become a topic of the times before us.

7.1 The integration and symbiosis of the sense of community, shared spiritual home, and national identity of the Chinese nation

The sense of community of the Chinese nation is the foundation of national unity, the basis of ethnic solidarity, and the soul of spiritual strength. It embodies the consciousness of a community of shared destiny, emphasizing that as a community, the future and destiny of 56 ethnic groups are closely linked to the future and destiny of the country. The formation of this consciousness is not only a subjective understanding of the objective existence of the Chinese national community, but also a process of recognizing, evaluating, and identifying with the Chinese national community in social practice activities.

The common spiritual home of the Chinese nation is the sum of the cultural spirit, values and emotional attitudes that the community can rely on, be willing to inherit and carry forward together. It represents the spiritual driving force of the Chinese nation's endless vitality, unity, and progress, composed of a common cultural foundation, a common national spirit, and a common pursuit of ideals. In this spiritual home, the excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation plays a pivotal role, accumulating the deepest spiritual pursuits of the Chinese nation and containing the fundamental spiritual genes of the Chinese nation.

Chinese national identity is an ideological and emotional connection formed by people within a certain ethnic group, which is the sense of identity and pride that people hold towards their own nation. The formation of this sense of identity cannot be separated from the guidance of the sense of community of the Chinese nation and the nourishment of the shared spiritual home of the Chinese nation.

From this, it can be seen that there is a close and complex relationship between the sense of community of the Chinese nation, the shared spiritual home of the Chinese nation, and the identity of the Chinese nation. Community consciousness is the ideological foundation of building a spiritual home, which is the fertile ground for the growth of community consciousness and national identity. National identity is the ultimate goal and value pursuit of community consciousness and spiritual home construction.

7.2 Enhancing national identity and community consciousness in the construction of a shared spiritual home for the Chinese nation

Building a shared spiritual home for the Chinese nation is an important way to enhance Chinese national identity and strengthen the sense of community among the Chinese nation. Specifically, we can start from the following aspects:

Firstly, we should deeply explore and inherit the excellent traditional cultures of various ethnic groups, strengthen the protection of intangible cultural heritage, and promote cultural exchanges and mutual learning among all ethnic groups. Through cultural exchange and integration, enhance the sense of cultural identity and belonging among various ethnic groups, and promote the formation of a sense of community among the Chinese nation.

Secondly, organize various ethnic unity and progress themed activities, such as knowledge competitions, speech contests, essay contests, etc., to enhance the sense of community of the Chinese nation among all ethnic groups. These activities not only enhance understanding and friendship among people of all ethnic groups, but also inspire their enthusiasm and motivation to jointly maintain national unity and ethnic solidarity.

In addition, strengthening the promotion and implementation of ethnic policies and regulations is also an indispensable part. By thoroughly promoting the Party's ethnic policies, people of all ethnic groups can fully understand and recognize China's ethnic policies, thereby enhancing their sense of identity and belonging to the Chinese national community.

7.3 The basic path and substantive connotation of building a community of the Chinese nation

Building a community in the Chinese nation is a systematic project that requires starting from multiple aspects. The basic path includes strengthening education on ethnic unity and progress, promoting economic and social development in ethnic areas, and governing ethnic affairs in accordance with the law. Through the implementation of these paths, we can gradually build a united, harmonious, and prosperous community of the Chinese nation.

The essence of building a community of the Chinese nation lies in achieving mutual integration of interests and interconnected destinies among all ethnic groups, promoting common development, mutual benefit and sharing among all ethnic groups. This requires us to adhere to the principle of equality and mutual respect among all ethnic groups, promote the inclusiveness and exchange of ethnic cultures, strengthen confidence in Chinese culture, and ensure the prosperity and development of the Chinese nation.

At present, the two special administrative regions of Hong Kong and Macao have deeply integrated into the overall development of the country, and the construction of the Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Greater Bay Area is constantly advancing. The construction of the Taiwan Strait Economic Cooperation Zone is also being promoted. The South China Economic Circle and the Fujian Taiwan Economic Zone have a "five cultural ties" of kinship, geography, cultural ties, material ties, and business ties. It is possible and necessary to establish a "Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Min Taiwan Chinese Ethnic Community Construction Pilot Zone" based on this "five cultural ties" to explore regional practices in the construction of the Chinese ethnic community in the southern and southeastern coastal areas. On the basis of the 1992 Consensus, we will continue to promote the all-round integration of politics, economy, society and culture between the two sides of the Taiwan Straits and the Hong Kong, Macao and Taiwan regions with the Chinese Mainland, so as to promote the "One China" construction of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

7.4 Strengthening the Awareness of the Chinese National Community and Building the Chinese National Community: The Intrinsic Requirements and Cultural Consciousness of the Great Rejuvenation of the Chinese Nation

From forging a strong sense of community for the Chinese nation to building a community for the Chinese nation, it is not only an inevitable requirement for maintaining national unity and ethnic solidarity, but also an inherent

requirement for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation. In this process, China's reform and opening up, as well as the smooth progress of the two "centenary goals," have demonstrated profound cultural consciousness.

Cultural self-awareness refers to people living in a certain culture having a "self-awareness" of its origin, formation process, characteristics, and development trends. In the practice of building a community of the Chinese nation, we deeply recognize the unique value and charm of Chinese culture, actively inherit and promote excellent traditional Chinese culture, and enhance cultural identity and confidence. This cultural consciousness not only helps us better understand and strengthen the sense of community of the Chinese nation, but also provides strong spiritual motivation and cultural support for realizing the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation.

In summary, from strengthening the awareness of building a community of the Chinese nation to constructing a community of the Chinese nation is a complex and profound process that involves multiple aspects such as culture, ethnicity, and politics. By deeply exploring and inheriting the excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation, organizing various themed activities on ethnic unity and progress, and strengthening the promotion and implementation of ethnic policies and regulations, we can continuously enhance the identity of the Chinese nation and forge a sense of community for the Chinese nation. At the same time, we should also recognize the essence and value pursuit of this process, which is to achieve mutual integration of interests and interdependence of destinies among various ethnic groups, and promote the common prosperity and development of the Chinese nation. This is not only an inherent requirement for the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, but also reflects the profound cultural consciousness and firm cultural confidence of the Chinese nation.

8. Conclusion

As a great initiative of socialism with Chinese characteristics, "One Country, Two Systems" not only successfully solved the governance problems after the return of Hong Kong and Macao, but also profoundly influenced the national process of the Chinese nation. Through institutional arrangements, political integration, economic integration, and social and cultural exchanges, "One Country, Two Systems" has promoted close ties and coordinated development between Hong Kong, Macao, and the mainland, enhancing the political identity, economic process, and social and cultural identity of the Chinese nation.

There is a complex and profound dialectical relationship between ethnic processes and nation states. Through the integration and recognition of political, economic, social, and cultural dimensions, nation states can achieve harmonious coexistence and common development among various ethnic groups. In the future, with the deepening development of globalization, multi-ethnic countries should pay more attention to the dynamic management of ethnic processes and the deepening construction of national identity to cope with new challenges and opportunities. Although this article provides a relatively systematic analysis of the dialectical relationship between ethnic processes and nation states, there are still many issues worth exploring in depth. For example, how to maintain the uniqueness and diversity of national culture in the context of globalization? How to build a more effective ethnic policy system to promote equality and integration among all ethnic groups? These issues require further research and exploration by experts and scholars.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization & Methodology, LIAO, Yang and MENG, Li; Formal Analysis, LIAO, Yang; .; Resources, MENG, Li; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, LIAO, Yang and MENG, Li; Writing – Review & Editing, LIAO, Yang; Supervision, MENG, Li.; Project Administration, LIAO, Yang; Funding Acquisition, LIAO, Yang”.

Funding: This study is supported by the Humanities and Social Sciences Planning Fund of the Ministry of Education of China, with funding number 22YJA850007, and the Guangdong Research Base for United Front Work Theory in Hong Kong, Macao, and Overseas of the China United Front Theory Research Association, with funding numbers TZKT2314 and TZKT2418

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest. The funding sponsors had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, and in the decision to publish the results.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics approval: Not applicable.

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